

IMPLEMENTATION OF JPEG-2000 USING FPGA

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ABSTRACT:

JPEG 2000 is an upcoming image compression standard published by the committee of JPEG, Joint Photographic Experts Group, to serve the needs of current and future applications that use still image coding.

The JPEG-2000 codec is transform-based. It employs multicomponent transforms, wavelet transforms, and bit-plane coding techniques in order to provide a framework for both lossy and lossless compression. Here, we have presented an overview and implementation of the jpeg 2000 coder, which caters to the needs of numerous applications.

KEYWORDS: *Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT), Lifting Scheme, Jpeg2000, VLSI Architectures*

BACKGROUND:

Advancements in the field of digital communication, along with the increase in mobile traffic, have increased the need for standards and systems with lower bit rates for efficient usage of the channel for data transmission [5]. In an application where multimedia is to be transmitted over a channel or is to be

stored in an environment with limited storage resources, the need for data compression systems increases further. The need for an efficient compression scheme can be emphasized by the fact that if an uncompressed video file were to be stored on a compact disc, it would barely hold about 5 to 10 minutes of low-resolution video without any sound /audio associated with it.

Image compression is important in commercial, industrial, and academic applications. Whether it is in commercial photography, industrial imaging, or video, digital pixel information can comprise considerably large amounts of data. Management of such data can involve significant overhead in computational complexity, storage, and data processing. Typical access speeds for storage mediums are inversely proportional to capacity. Through data compression, such tasks can be optimized. Image and video compressors and decompresses (codecs) are implemented mainly in software, as digital signal processors have optimized instruction sets to manage the required operations. Hardware-specific codecs can be integrated into digital systems fairly easily, requiring work only in the areas of interface and overall integration. Improvements in speed occur primarily because the hardware can be tailored to

the compression algorithm as well as the application. Using an FPGA to implement a codec combines the better of two worlds: significantly increased processing speed due to the use of customized hardware and flexibility to make changes and tunings of the algorithm since FPGA-based designs are easily modified [6].

AIM OF THE PROJECT

To design and implement JPEG using VHDL on FPGA. The software implementation provides the advantage of reconfigurability at the code level but is inherently slow. The FPGA Implementation overcomes this problem by providing a high degree of reconfigurability at the design level and also provides efficient and fast implementation on hardware. By exploring the basic algorithm [2] and the computations that go into the encoding of an image, an efficient means to encode an image is being studied which is discussed in brief in this report. The software modules would be used to build the VHDL modules for the various modules in the encoder.

Introduction to Jpeg 2000 standard

JPEG 2000 is the next ISO/ITU-T standard for still image coding. In the following, we restrict the description to Part I of the standard, which defines the core system [1]. Part II will provide various extensions for specific applications but is still in preparation. JPEG 2000 is based on the discrete wavelet transform (DWT), scalar quantization, context modelling, arithmetic coding and post-compression rate allocation [2]. The DWT is dyadic and can be performed with either the reversible Le Gall (5, 3) taps filter,

which provides for lossless coding, or the non-reversible Daubechies (9, 7) taps biorthogonal one, which provides for higher compression but does not do lossless. The quantizer follows an embedded dead-zone scalar approach and is independent for each sub-band. Each sub-band is divided into rectangular blocks (called code-blocks in JPEG 2000), typically 64x64, and entropy-coded using context modelling and bit-plane arithmetic coding. The coded data is organized in so-called layers, which are quality levels, using the post-compression rate allocation and output to the code-stream in packets. The generated code stream is parseable and can be resolution, layer (i.e. SNR), position or component progressive, or any combination thereof.

JPEG 2000 also supports a number of functionalities, many of which are inherent in the algorithm itself [2]. An example of this is random access, which is possible because of the independent coding of the code blocks and the packetized structure of the codestream. Such functionality is the possibility to encode images with arbitrarily shaped Regions of Interest (ROI) [9]. The fact that the subbands are encoded bitplane by bitplane makes it possible to select regions of the image that will precede the rest of the image in the codestream. By scaling the sub-band samples so that the bitplanes encoded first only contain ROI information and the following bitplanes only contain background information. The only thing the decoder needs to receive is the factor by which the samples were scaled. The decoder can then invert the scaling based only on the amplitude of the samples.

Fig 1: shows the coding steps for the JPEG2000 algorithm

Fig 2: jpeg 2000 encoder

Functional Description

The JPEG2K-E operates either on an entire image or on a rectangular section of an image called a tile. The maximum supported image or tile size depends on the size of the external memory. With enough external memory, the core can support up to 4096x4096 images. The default configuration of the core embeds an SDRAM controller. However, JPEG2K-E configurations working with DDR/DDR2, or SRAM or QDR-SRAM can be made available on demand. The JPEG2K-E consists of several functional blocks, as shown in the block diagram [10] and briefly explained here. As encoding begins, the input pixels are first level-shifted and then transformed using either the reversible 5/3 or the

irreversible 9/7 two-dimensional discrete wavelet transform. The transformed coefficients are stored in the external memory. After an entire tile has been transformed, the transformed coefficients are quantized. The quantized coefficients are fed to the Entropy Coding Engines on a code-block per code-block basis.

The coded segments, along with the code-block attributes (truncation lengths and distortion metrics) produced by the Entropy Coding Engines, are fed to the Rate Control Engine. If enabled, the Rate Control Engine implements a proprietary PCRD algorithm that outputs a code stream at the required compression ratio with the minimum possible loss of quality. Finally, the Headers-Syntax Unit forms global, tile and packet headers and outputs a compliant stream or file. This may be omitted from the core if it is not needed. The image decomposition using a 9/7 filter is performed as shown in Fig [4].

$$\lambda = 4, \quad A_0(z) = \alpha_0(z + 1), \quad A_1(z) = \alpha_1(1 + z^{-1}), \quad ($$

$$A_2(z) = \alpha_2(z + 1), \quad A_3(z) = \alpha_3(1 + z^{-1}),$$

$$Q_i(x) = x \quad \text{for } i = 0, 1, 2, 3,$$

$$\alpha_0 \approx -1.586134, \quad \alpha_1 \approx -0.052980, \quad \alpha_2 \approx 0.882911,$$

$$\alpha_3 \approx 0.443506, \quad s_0 \approx 1.230174, \quad s_1 = 1/s_0.$$

DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

The objective of the proposed DWT design is to allow maximum flexibility while maximizing memory efficiency. Requirements for a flexible design include the ability to utilize any user-defined wavelet. To accomplish this, the

DWT core is preconfigured with a set of lifting and scaling steps. In order to configure the DWT core for a particular wavelet, the lifting step extraction must be performed prior to configuration to obtain the necessary lifting and scaling steps. An arbitrary number of lifting steps can be defined, and the number of scaling steps needed is two. The lifting/scaling steps are defined by real number Signed coefficients. Each lifting step can use a rounding function, as required by the particular wavelet [3].

The inputs and outputs of the DWT core are preconfigured to define various parameters, such as the maximum image width and height allowed, the maximum number of levels of decomposition possible, and the size of memory, data and address bus. Once the DWT core is configured and implemented in hardware, many options are available at run-time. The DWT core can perform both the forward and inverse DWT on an image of any height or width. The DWT core can also perform the DWT on local smaller portions of the image. This is particularly useful for cases where the DWT is applied to one or more tiles of an image, as is the case with JPEG2000 [1]. Finally, the DWT core is portable. Since it is written in standard hardware description language, it can be ported to various types of hardware, such as FPGAs and Asics. Memory efficiency is one of the goals of the present design. This was accomplished by performing computations in place, minimizing the amount of image buffering, and reducing the amount of swap memory space. The proposed wavelet core implements the "line-based" DWT in a manner that requires only one pass per row/column. As a result, however, each lifting step requires separate multiplication units. Since the lifting step coefficients do not

change at run time, the DWT core uses fixed-point shift-add multiplier hardware that is specifically tuned for each lifting step coefficient instead of using regular floating-point multipliers for real number coefficients. These units automatically generate the necessary hardware to perform the multiplication of an integer number by any precision signed floating point number. These units are faster and use less area/power than general-purpose floating-point multipliers.

The inverse DWT using the lifting scheme is symmetrical and, therefore, performed by reversing the lifting steps in the forward DWT. The DWT core takes advantage of this by reusing the ALU components from the forward DWT by rerouting the data path in the reverse direction and changing the additions to subtractions and vice-versa. As a result, the additional hardware overhead in terms of control and routing for the reverse DWT is minimal.

APPLICATIONS

Application domain can be sub-divided into two groups [7]:

Porting JPEG2000 solution on embedded platforms for real-time applications.

Integrate JPEG2000 technology into primary products for further integration into product applications. For example, JPEG2000 Interactive Image Browser, JPEG2000 plug-in for graphics tools, MATLAB, Active-X, etc.

Applications that can exploit the capabilities of feature-rich JPEG2000 Image Standard to get the most out of its features. For example, Medical Imaging,

Remote Sensing, Geographical Information Systems (GIS), Digital Cinema and Mobile applications, etc. Applying imaging to modern applications will change the way we look at the world. Some of the unexplored areas where state-of-the-art JPEG2000 technology can be best used are:

- Digital Museums/Art Exhibitions
- Future Homes
- Classroom Environment

PROJECT PROGRESS, FUTURE WORK and CONCLUSION:

We are in the process of code development of the coder. We have learnt up to the transformation of the image using DWT; the arithmetic coding of the blocks of coefficients and their streaming part is left, after which it will be implemented using lattice FPGA and an image sensor for practical observations. It is expected that an input image from the sensor will be compressed and transmitted to the with less memory size than the original one the pc. The decoding process will be performed, and the image will be displayed on the PC. We drew a fourfold conclusion from this design experiment that has been derived. First, high-level design greatly benefits from advanced optimizations such as the reduction of memory accesses. Next, the use of a system-level design language requires a well-documented design methodology to be effective. Third, current FPGA-based design flows do not yet have the same ease of use as equivalent DSP-based design flows. Finally, gaps in the design flow have been a constant source of extra effort during the entire project. These gaps cause overhead because they require a rewrite of code, such as, for

instance, to go from SpecC to a DSP. A design flow must be closed to be fully effective.

General-purpose DSP implementations often lack the performance necessary for moderate sampling rates, and ASIC approaches are limited in flexibility and may not be cost-effective for many applications. Our example of JPEG 2000 implementation illustrates that the FPGA approach is both flexible and provides performance comparable to or superior to traditional approaches. Because of the programmability of this technology, the examples in this paper can be extended to provide a variety of high-performance JPEG algorithms.

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